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D.1.1

Quality and Risk Management Plan

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Author(s) – in alphabetical order		
Name	Organisation	E-mail
Panagiotis Lytrivis	ICCS	panagiotis.lytrivis@iccs.gr
Vasilis Surlas	ICCS	v.surlas@iccs.gr

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Abstract
This document, entitled “ <i>Quality and Risk Management Plan</i> ”, specifies the procedures to be applied by the ICT4CART partners and the ICT4CART governing bodies, in order to guarantee the high quality of project results and the easy monitoring of the project process.

Legal Disclaimer

The document reflects only the authors' view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
CA	Consortium Agreement
DCM	Dissemination and Communication Manager
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement/General Assembly
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IT	Information technology
L4	Forth Level of Driving automation for On-Road vehicles
LTE-V	Long-Term Evolution-Vehicle
PC	Project Coordinator
PMI	Project Management Institute
PO	Project officer
PU	Public
QRM	Quality and Risk Manager
RMP	Risk Management Plan
SC	Steering committee
SEI	Software Engineering Institute
SRE	Software Risk Evaluation
TIM	Technical and Innovation Manager
TL	Task Leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

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Executive Summary

The Quality and Risk management plan is a public document of the ICT4CART project; it is delivered in the context of the management work package, task T1.3: Quality and risk management, with the main objective to set up the project quality control procedures, monitor project milestones, create a risk register and define the appropriate mitigation strategies.

The document provides the quality control processes and risk management procedures, and can be considered complementary to the Description of Action (DoA) and Consortium Agreement (CA) with respect to quality assessment and risk control of a such an ambitious project as ICT4CART is. These procedures and rules will be the stepping stone for all ICT4CART project partners.

The document is structured in six sections. After a short introduction on the ICT4CART project and the purpose of the current report in Section 1, the organizational structure of the project is detailed described as a starting point for all processes in Section 2. Based on this structure, it is highlighted how quality management is embedded in the project including the allocation of responsibilities to the different roles, the decision making and communication procedures.

In Section 3, quality measures and related rules to assure high quality project deliverables are defined. Clearly specified document management and review processes, as well as criteria for the assignment of reviewers per deliverable, an indicative checklist for carrying out the review and the codification of the project documents are detailed described to ensure the high quality of the ICT4CART deliverables.

In Section 4, the quality assurance processes for dissemination material and activities are thoroughly described. This includes the key performance indicators relevant for publications and procedures for publication. A high quality of dissemination activities and material will support broad visibility and easy uptake of ICT4CART materials.

Risk management procedures are defined in Section 5. This includes the monitoring and identification of risks as well as risk assessment and mitigation measures. Proper risk management will contribute to decrease the impact of unforeseen events and to reach the objectives defined in the description of work.

Finally, Rules and conventions to support information exchange and communication in ICT4CART are described in Section 6. The procedures and processes described in this document may also be updated if additional needs arise during the execution of the project.

1 Introduction

1.1 Aim of the project

Today, significant and rapid advances in both telecom and IT industries can be accredited to fast-growing disruptive technologies. Amongst these, the ETSI ITS G5 technology appears to be quite mature. Moreover, the 5G technology is evolving rapidly, while LTE-Vehicle (LTE-V) features low cost and rapid deployment since it can utilize existing base stations. In the light also of the above, several ICT challenges related to connectivity, data management, cyber-security and ICT infrastructure architectures still play a significant role and need to be addressed in order to enable road vehicle automation. Thus, it is of utmost importance for the vehicle automation to work on the direction of advancing the digital and ICT infrastructure, taking also into consideration the limitations in both resources and investments, in the physical transport infrastructure.

ICT4CART aims to address the gaps to deployment bringing together key players from automotive, telecom and IT industries, to shape the ICT landscape for Connected and Automated Road Transport and to boost the EU competitiveness and innovation in this area.

The main goal of ICT4CART is to design, implement and test in real-life conditions a versatile ICT infrastructure that will enable the transition towards higher levels of automation (up to L4) addressing existing gaps and working with specific key ICT elements, namely hybrid connectivity, data management, cyber-security, data privacy and accurate localization. ICT4CART builds on high-value use cases (urban and highway), which will be demonstrated and validated in real-life conditions at the test sites in Austria, Germany and Italy. Significant effort will be put also on cross-border interoperability, setting up a separate test site at the Italian-Austrian border.

1.2 Purpose of the document

An essential measure to reach the highly ambitious and challenging objectives of the ICT4CART project is to set, well in advance, the appropriate quality management procedures and rules. These procedures and rules, detailed described in this document, will be the acting-basis for all ICT4CART project partners, in order to successfully ensure high quality project outcomes. If necessary, the present document will be further updated to reflect any changes that may occur during the project lifetime. This might especially be necessary once the technical implementation of ICT4CART have been further defined.

1.3 Intended readership

This deliverable is addressed to any interested reader (i.e., PU dissemination level). Compared to others, D1.1 can be practically useful for the consortium members who can use it as a basis for the general management of all project activities.

2 Quality Management in ICT4CART

2.1 Organization management of ICT4CART

The consortium is composed of an appropriate number of strong and complementary partners (21) who will deliver the project ambition and fulfil the project expectations and objectives. In order to guarantee and achieve an effective and efficient interaction between them and avoid any management difficulties, partners have agreed to follow a simple management hierarchy which will

ensure fast decision and smooth project management, while at the same time it will provide the necessary control and participation mechanisms. Three bodies will be responsible for decision making, namely: The Project Coordinator (PC), the Steering Committee (SC) and the General Assembly (GA). In the GA, each project partner is represented by one vote. The overall management structure of the project is depicted in Figure 1 and it is thoroughly described below:

Figure 1 – ICT4CART Management structure

The Project Coordinator (ICCS)

The Project Coordinator (PC) – **Dr. Angelos Amditis** – is responsible for the coordination of the activities under the contract with the European Commission (EC) and the overall project monitoring and supervision. Thus, PC has the overall administrative and financial responsibility for the organisation, planning and controlling of the project. The PC will interact with the EC and third parties about the project, including the submission of the deliverables to the EC. In addition to his obligations under the Grant Agreement, the PC will receive, compile and distribute to all beneficiaries, documents, reports, statements of expenditures and minutes of meetings of the SC and GA, as well as any other corresponding information received from contributors.

The Technical and Innovation Manager (NOKIA)

The Technical and Innovation Manager (TIM) – **Mr. Birger Hättö** – is taking care of all technical and innovation management activities in ICT4CART. The main responsibilities of the TIM are:

- Implementation of the overall technical coordination strategy and management;
- Coordination of technical activities between Work Packages and test sites;
- Work with PC and WPLs to plan, monitor and direct all technical aspects of the project;
- Coordinate all relevant technical development partners to ensure that technical milestones are achieved on time and according to specifications laid down in the workplan;
- Moderate on technical decisions and moderate in case of conflicting choices with regards to technical developments;
- Manage the knowledge produced during the project lifecycle with the goal of successfully implementing innovative ideas, assess the opportunity for applying for patents or declaring copyrights and allow the consortium to respond to an external or internal opportunity;
- Ensure the protection of Intellectual Property.

- Monitor the project to guarantee consistency between technical and marketing choices;
- Assure the successful implementation of innovative ideas by the design and implementation of an effective innovation management system.
- Identify trends and technologies which could be of interest for the project
- Coordinate and supervise the preparation of the project exploitation strategy.

The Risk and Quality Manager (ICCS)

The Quality and Risk Manager (QRM) is responsible for formulating a detailed Quality Control Strategy and setting the quality criteria for each deliverable in order to assure the conformity of all project documentation with the initial DoA guidelines, and to guarantee that they are in conformity with the project grant agreement. QRM is also responsible for updating the risk registry and creating a mitigation strategy plan. The appointed QRM in ICT4CART is **Dr. Panagiotis Lytrivis (ICCS)**.

The Dissemination and Communication Manager (ERTICO)

The Dissemination and Communication Manager (DCM), undertaken by **Mrs. Cordelia Wilson (ERTICO)**, is coordinating all issues related to dissemination and communication activities. The DCM will oversee the entire process and will be responsible for internal reporting and management. The DCM will be the main point of contact for day-to-day communications matters as well as maintenance of the website, social media sites, video coordination, press liaison and networking and cross fertilization activities.

The Steering Committee

The Steering Committee (SC) is composed of the PC, the TIM, the DCM, the QRM and the WP leaders. The SC is responsible for the facilitation of the project management and will supervise the progress of the project from its start up to its completion, guaranteeing its continuity and consistency and allocating the resources adequately. It will be in charge of implementing the general decisions taken by the GA and will not interfere with internal WP issues, unless these disturb the project or other WPs, and will handle any conflict resolution within the project that could not be handled at a lower level. The SC will meet twice a year with at least one meeting being physical; the chairperson will be the PC.

The General Assembly

The General Assembly (GA) is the superior governing body of ICT4CART. The GA must review the project progress with regard to its goals and achievements, will decide on contingency actions in case of major deviations from plan, and will take final decisions on policy and contractual issues and conflicts as requested by the PC. It will be comprised of one delegate per member organisation and will convene physically once per year and virtually –when needed-, including the possibility of using online tools to facilitate quick decision-making. Each delegate will have one vote; decisions will be made by consensus whenever possible. Only in cases where no consensus is possible, decisions will be made by majority voting. Details for voting are laid down in the ICT4CART Consortium Agreement.

The Work Package Leaders

Work Package Leaders (WPLs) are responsible for coordinating the technical work within their respective WPs, in close collaboration with the TIM. WPLs set WP objectives, oversee milestones and are responsible for monitoring progress. Each task within the WP has a defined leader and it is up to the WPL to coordinate the activities between task leaders (TLs). TLs report directly to the WPLs who

in turn report to the PC, SC and GA. WPLs are responsible for:

- Coordinating the activities of task leaders;
- Presenting progress reports at meetings and contributing to management reports;
- Documenting any major decisions to a deviation of the already defined work plan;
- Reporting to PC any partner whose contributions are considered insufficient.

The Task Leaders

Task Leaders (TLs) have to manage, supervise, monitor the activities within their tasks and produce the corresponding deliverables associated with their tasks. They are responsible for the timely completion of the activities within their tasks and for supporting the WPLs in managing the WPs by contributing to annual reports, adhering to budget guidelines and informing the WPLs of any deviations from the work plan.

The aforementioned lean structure is considered sufficient to manage ICT4CART, towards the definition of clear roles and responsibilities for each partner and project body. It also allows cost-effective management of the project while ensuring timely delivery of high quality results and early warning if any deviations from the work plan may occur.

2.2 Management procedures of ICT4CART

2.2.1 Decision making

The project management structure follows clear levels of decision making, with defined roles and responsibilities of each participated body. All strategic decisions are made by the GA, which also monitors the project performance. The overall administration and coordination of the project is carried out by the PC with support from the SC. On work package level, management is carried out by the WPLs and the TLs. In case of disagreement at any level, the decision will be deferred to the next level. In case that no decision can be reached on the level of the GA, the conflict will be presented to the EC project officer by the PC. The full mechanism of decision making and resolving of conflicts is detailed described in the project Consortium Agreement.

Process for initiate /planning of WPs and Tasks

- The Coordinator requests WP leaders to initiate Tasks in their WP and to coordinate Task leaders work.
- WP leaders ask Task leaders to initiate Tasks and coordinate Task leaders work.
- WP leaders come back with working document/detailed Task plans of the work to be performed, including allocation of responsibilities among partners involved in the WP.

Process for WPs and Tasks performance reporting

- Each partner responsible for performing part of a Task prepares every 6 months a report for the coming 6-month WP internal report, so that the WP leader and the coordinator can track the performance of the task.
- If one or more Tasks result into a deliverable, the deliverable main author synthesises the Tasks internal reports into the expected deliverable.
- The deliverable main author submits the deliverable for peer review.
- As soon as all deliverables in a WP, which have been submitted to the European Commission through the Coordinator (after having been peer reviewed), have been accepted by the European Commission, the WP is terminated.

2.2.2 Project meetings and communication procedures and tools

Regular communication through both physical and virtual meetings is considered as a vital procedure for the project. The GA, which is the main decision body of the project, will be met physically at least once per year, while virtual meetings can be requested by any partner if there is a need. The SC will be met at least twice a year (next to an event) and will hold regular virtual conferences. In order to reduce travel costs, the aim is to have one of these meetings coinciding with the annual GA meeting. In addition, kick-off and final meeting will also be physical meetings, although one of them could also be combined with a GA meeting. Technical meetings on work package level will be carried out in regular intervals, both physical and virtual, whatever is deemed most appropriate by the respective WPLs. E-mail, web-conferencing and telephone will be the primary means for internal communication and document exchange. A web conference tool (e.g., GoToMeeting, Skype, etc.) will be used for online meetings. At each meeting minutes will be kept and made available within the consortium. The project will use also a web-based tool (Redmine) as a document repository and file exchange system, ensuring both safe storage of documents and supporting efficient collaboration among partners.

Process for meetings organisation

Meetings are organised for certifying the status of the project, as well as for decision making. The process for meetings organisation is as follows:

1. The physical or virtual meetings of the General Assembly (GA) and the Steering Committee (SC), are convened and organised by the Coordinator. The physical or virtual meetings of one WP/Task are convened and organised by the WP/Task leader.
 - 1.1. Forty-five calendar days before each scheduled **General Assembly** physical or virtual meeting (fifteen days for an extraordinary meeting) the Organiser issues a meeting notice and invites the participants by sending also an agenda (twenty-one days before the meeting or ten in extraordinary events), including the items to be discussed and the decisions proposed to be made. The first discussion item of the agenda must be the actions status.
 - 1.2. Fourteen calendar days before each scheduled **Steering Committee** physical or virtual meeting (seven days for an extraordinary meeting), the Organiser issues a meeting notice and invites the participants by sending also an agenda (seven days before the meeting), including the items to be discussed and the decisions proposed to be made. The first discussion item of the agenda must be the actions status. The same procedure also applies to any WP or Task specific physical or virtual meeting.
2. Recipients should send comments on the agenda within 5 working days.
3. The Organiser updates the agenda and submits the final version at least 5 working days before the meeting.
4. Modality (face to face meetings or conference call), duration and venue of the meetings shall be proposed by the convener and communicated along with the updated agenda
5. During the meeting, the Organiser is responsible for keeping the minutes of the meeting. Minutes shall include decisions made and actions list defined.
6. The Organiser uploads the draft meeting minutes, on the Redmine and informs the participants within 10 calendar days after the end of the meeting. Minutes must at least contain:
 - The attendees list
 - The agenda
 - Decision taken
 - Action list along with the responsible person for each action
7. Recipients should send comments on the minutes within 15 calendar days. The minutes shall be considered as accepted if, within 15 calendar days from sending, no Member has sent an objection in writing to the organizer with respect to the accuracy of the draft of the minutes.
8. The Organiser uploads the final accepted meeting minutes in the Redmine and informs the whole Consortium within 2 working days.

Process for WP and Task meetings organisation

1. WP and Task meetings are organised by the WPLs and Task leaders respectively.
2. The frequency of the meeting is decided by the WPLs and Task leaders, but it is advisable to celebrate a meeting at least once per month, most preferably via conference call.
3. An agenda should be circulated among the participants at least one week in advance.
4. During the meeting, the Organiser is responsible for keeping the minutes of the meeting. Minutes shall include decisions made and actions list defined.
5. Minutes of meeting are transmitted to the attendees within 3 days after the meeting.

The periods specified in this section could be adjusted if unanimously agreed by all members of the given body.

Process for internal six-monthly reporting and monitoring

All participants are requested to send a brief technical and financial report for the work performed and resources spent per each active WP to the Coordinator and the relevant WP leader, every 6 months. The WP leaders may use these forms to produce warning milestones for the Coordinator and the particular Partner(s) involved, if for example there is an overspending in resources which does not correspond to concrete outputs of work. Also, when other key issues/problems are found, the reports will be further evaluated and may cause alarm warnings by the WP leader. For any issues/problems may occur on the reporting of the WP activities, WP leaders should always inform the Coordinator.

Six-monthly Progress Reports

The procedure to be followed for the six-monthly progress reports within the ICT4CART project is the following:

- The Coordinator initiates the reporting process by sending out a request for six-monthly technical report and time plan to all partners.
- Partners create one Report, with the technical work they performed per each active WP and they send it to the relevant WP leaders.
- WP leaders review the work presented per Partner and compile one integrated report per WP with the feedback of each participating Partner included.
- The integrated report per WP is sent by the WP leader to Coordinator.
- The Coordinator gathers all reports, integrates them and prepares the consolidated report. It uploads it in the Redmine and informs all Partners.

Six-Monthly Financial Reports

All partners report estimations of person months spent for each reporting period (i.e., the past six months). These will be estimations as the exact figures will be provided in the official periodic reports. The procedure followed for the six-monthly financial reports within the ICT4CART project is the following:

- The Coordinator initiates the reporting process by sending out a request for six-monthly financial report and time plan to all partners.
- Partners fill in the fields of the tables of an excel sheet for the reporting period, referring in specific to the person months that have been spent per WP, and they upload it on the Redmine, informing the relevant WP leaders and the Coordinator.
- WP leaders review the reported resources by each Partner and they send their comments if they note any discrepancy between costs and work conducted to the Coordinator.
- The Coordinator gathers all reports, integrates them and prepares the financial report. It uploads it in the Redmine and informs all Partners.
- Partners send any comments on the integrated financial report before its finalisation by the

Coordinator.

Communication protocols

Files will not be circulated as attachments to e-mails, but will be uploaded to the Redmine repository at the adequate location. Afterwards, a notification e-mail will be sent to all partners concerned (a separate mailing list has been created for each WP, the SC and one for Administrative issues), including a short description of file contents and respective Redmine links. The consortium partners will use a variety of tools for communicating, exchange/store files and taking decision on day to day management issues. The tools and means to be used for internal communication are listed below:

- Virtual meetings to be organised via GoToMeeting or other web meeting tool available to each chairman convening a meeting.
- Doodle or other online voting tools to be used for voting and taking decisions.
- Redmine to be used as document repository.

The main software standards have been defined as follows:

- Operating System: Windows or Linux;
- MS Word: textual deliverable for working documents;
- pdf for final deliverables to be delivered and distributed externally
- MS Excel: textual deliverable support, cost statement, etc.;
- MS PowerPoint: transparencies, slides, posters, etc.;
- Alternative systems fully compatible with the above mentioned.

2.3 Embedding quality management in ICT4CART

Each project partner is responsible to contribute to the overall quality of the project outputs. In addition, specific roles and responsibilities have been clearly assigned to ensure effective quality management for all key aspects of the project (see **Error! Reference source not found.**).

Table 1 – Roles and responsibilities in ICT4CART

Role in Project	Responsible for
Project coordinator (PC) - ICCS	Overall responsibility
Technical and innovation manager (TIM) - NOKIA	Technical developments and outputs
Risk and Quality Manager - ICCS	Quality of timely submission of the deliverables
Leader of WP Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (QRM) - ERTICO	Coordination of all communication and dissemination activities
Work package leaders (WPLs)	Responsible to carry out the assigned work package in sufficient quality and in the expected time frame.
Task leaders (TLs)	Responsible to carry out the assigned tasks in sufficient quality and in the expected time frame.
Reviewers of deliverables	Responsible to assure that only high-quality deliverables are handed over.
Project partners	Must ensure that all ethical requirements (as described in D10.1-2) are met. In case of doubts the partner must inform the PC in order to solve open issues. In any case, if ethical issues are encountered, these must be communicated to the PC who will document on how these issues were addressed in the project.

Tracking of progress and use of resources is based on a half year reporting (i.e., reports presented in Section 2.2.2). This reporting consists of two parts, information on resources used and activities carried out including any deviations to the work plan. The templates for this reporting will be provided to the project partners. Each partner must send this information two weeks before the semi-annual project management team meetings to the coordinator and to the technical manager. In case of major deviations the coordinator and the technical manager must be informed as soon as they become apparent.

3 Quality assurance of deliverables

Deliverables are a key element of the project. They are used to provide information on project developments and results to the public but also to hand over definitions, results, etc. to other work packages and tasks in the project. Therefore, quality assurance process focuses on formulating a strategy to ensure high quality of deliverables and conformity with the Grand Agreement. For that purpose, two main processes are described: the document management process and the deliverable review process. The first one aims at defining the procedures need to be followed for the production and the management of a deliverable while the second process targets in checking the deliverable compliance with the quality standards defined for the project.

3.1 Document management process

The QRM is responsible for ensuring that all documents are consistent and easily traceable through a unique codification. There are two levels of control by the QRM.

- Level 1: The control of deliverables registration and all documents referencing;
- Level 2: The control of consistency of documents layout and appropriate storing inside the project repository

3.1.1 Document referencing

There will be a unique project document coding system for all internal documents, as indicated in Table 2 below. The following does not apply to official project deliverables. The nomenclature of deliverables is presented in section 3.1.2. The unique document referencing scheme is not applicable for informal data and views exchange between Partners via simple e-mail.

Table 2 – ICT4CART project document coding system

Document Code	Document Type	Template to be used
RR	Deliverable Review Report	Peer Review Report Template (Annex B)
IR	Internal Technical Report	ICT4CART Deliverable/Word template (Annex A)
PR	Work Package Plans and Progress Reports	ICT4CART Deliverable/Word template (Annex A)
A	Meeting agendas	Meeting Agenda Template (Annex C)
M	Minutes, Action Lists, Decision Lists	Meeting Minutes Template (Annex D)
6TR	6monthly technical progress report	Six-Monthly Technical Progress Report Template (Annex E)
6FR	6monthly financial report	Six-Monthly Financial Report Template (Annex F)
C	Correspondence between Partners	ICT4CART Deliverable/Word template

		(Annex A)
L	Legal documents	ICT4CART Deliverable/Word template (Annex A)
GI	Documents of general interest	ICT4CART Deliverable/Word template (Annex A)
OTH	Other subjects	ICT4CART Deliverable/Word template (Annex A)

The codification for the names of the project internal documents (except from official Deliverables) follows below (table 3).

Table 3 – ICT4CART internal documents coding scheme

Position	Entry
First digits :	"ICT4CART"
Underscore	
Next 3-7 digits :	Abbreviated name of the author Partner (e.g. ICCS, ASFINAG)
Underscore	
Next 2-3 digits :	Type of document as in Error! Reference source not found. Error! Reference source not found.
Underscore	
Next digits :	Level in project hierarchy: "GA" means that the document content focuses on GA issues; "SC" means that the document content focuses on SC issues; "WPx" means that the document content focuses on WPx issues; This should not be confused with the dissemination of the document (Public or Confidential).
Underscore	
Next digits :	"v" and number of revision <X.X> of this specific report.
Underscore	
Next digits :	The document save date, "yyyymmdd".
Underscore	
Next digits :	Short explanatory title for the document. In case of meetings this can be the location and date of the meeting.

Example: "ICT4CART_ICCS_M_GA_v1.0_20180912_KoM minute" The final version of the KoM minutes. The version number will be set to 1.0 when the document has been finalized.

3.1.2 Deliverable nomenclature

In order to ensure consistency, a template for all ICT4CART deliverables is available at internal document repository. The filename of deliverables must adhere to the following codification

Table 4 – ICT4CART Deliverables coding scheme

Position	Entry
First digits :	"ICT4CART"
Underscore	
Next 3-4 digits :	"D" + <X.X> deliverable number according to the Description of Action
Underscore	

Next digits :	Deliverable title as in the Description of Action
Underscore	
Next 2-3 digits :	"v" and number of revision of the deliverable.
Underscore	
Next digits :	The document save date, "yyyymmdd".

Example: "ICT4CART_D1.1_Quality and Risk Management Plan_v0.1_20180925)". The version number of the deliverable will be set to 1.0 after the deliverable has been approved.

3.1.3 List of templates to be used

The templates, which correspond to each type of document that is foreseen to be circulated in terms of the ICT4CART project, are provided as Annexes of the present document.

The types of documents, addressing both internal communication and official documentation towards the EC, are namely:

- Annex A: ICT4CART Deliverable/Word Template
- Annex B: Deliverable Review Report Template
- Annex C: Meeting Agenda Template
- Annex D: Meeting Minutes Template
- Annex E: Six-Monthly Technical Progress Report Template
- Annex F: Six-Monthly Financial Report Template
- Annex G: Slides/Presentation template

3.2 Deliverable review process

The deliverable review process ensures the high quality of the project deliverables, which should meet the expectations of project objectives and results as defined in the Grand Agreement. It also improves the quality of the project outputs and it minimizes the risks of rejections.

Once the deliverable final draft is ready the review process is initiated. The following description shows the steps of the Deliverable review process along with an estimation (in calendar days) for each step:

1. **Draft version** (the deliverable is considered ready for submission by the partner responsible for the deliverable: Deliverable Leader): the deliverable is handed over to the Quality Manger, who contacts the internal reviewers and at the same time to all partners 30 calendar days before the due date (this follows the dissemination rules defined in the consortium).
2. **Internal review**: Internal reviewers carry out a review of the deliverable, using the Peer Review Evaluation form (*Annex A: Peer Review Report Template*) and must send their comments and recommendations for refinements –if necessary- to the authors for the deliverable and a copy to the technical manager and to the coordinator (10 days after receipt). Partners wishing to comment on the deliverable can do so within 10 days by sending the comments directly to the authors. For each deliverable two reviewers are assigned. Criteria for the selection of reviewers are that they are not the main authors of the document and, if applicable, reviewers' organization is a user of the output of the deliverable in a later stage of the project.

The reviewers after having studied the Deliverable, must evaluate it with respect to the following issues and must conclude whether the deliverable is accepted or not.

- General comments:
 - Deliverable contents thoroughness;
 - Correspondence to project objectives as in the Description of Action;

- Correspondence to programme objectives.
 - Specific comments:
 - Relevance;
 - Response to user needs;
 - Methodological framework soundness;
 - Quality of achievements;
 - Quality of presentation of achievements;
 - Deliverable layout (format, language, spelling, etc.).
 - The final rating of the Deliverable draft will be marked as:
 - Fully accepted
 - Accepted with reservation (minor comments/changes)
 - Rejected unless modified as suggested
 - Fully Rejected
3. Within 10 days after receipt of comments a new draft based on comments from reviewers and project partners have to be provided to the internal reviewers and the project coordinator and to the technical manager. In case of disagreement between authors and reviewers the technical manager and the coordinator must be involved.
 4. If all comments have been addressed properly the deliverable is uploaded to the EC portal by the project coordinator. Otherwise an additional review cycle has to be carried out (step 3).

The deliverable review process is represented graphically in the following figure 2.

Figure 2 – Deliverable review process

4 Quality assurance of dissemination material and activities

4.1 Key performance indicators

The effectiveness of ICT4CART strategic approach and planning for communication and dissemination will be constantly evaluated through dedicated performance indicators that are shown below and will be thoroughly reported in the D9.1 and its periodic updates.

Conference and Networking

- International Conference participants (estimate: 120)
- Demonstration events organized in the ICT4CART test sites (estimate: 3)
- People attending the Demonstration events organized in the ICT4CART test sites (estimate: 50 per event)
- Conference presentations (estimate: 47)
- Organisation of workshops/special sessions (estimate: 4)
- Number of EU and national projects networked (estimate: 10)
- Number of organisations/associations/platforms networked (estimate: 8)
- Number of liaison activities performed (estimate: 20)
- Number of discussions in fora, committees & organisations (estimate:12)
- Number of standardisation bodies and TCs networked (estimate: 5)

Website, Social Media, Press

- Visitors and page-views for the website (estimate: 100 per month)
- Contacts on social media (for specific platforms, for example: number of followers for Twitter)
- Quantity of media coverage achieved (estimate: 25)
- Social Media Campaigns (estimate: 2)
- Total number of e-newsletter recipients (estimate: 230)
- Number of journal articles (estimate: 4)
- Conference publications (estimate: 20)

4.2 Procedures for publications

Dissemination activities conditions are described in ICT4CART Consortium Agreement. Among other obligations and conditions agreed, the following excerpts have to be highlighted:

- During the Project and for a period of one (1) year after the end of the Project, the dissemination of own Results by one or several Parties including publications and presentations, shall be governed by the procedure of Article 29.1 of the Grant Agreement subject to the following provisions.
- Prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other Parties at least 28 calendar days before the publication, by making reference to the time period for objections. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement in writing to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 21 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.

An objection is justified if

- the protection of the objecting Party's Results or Background would be adversely affected
- the objecting Party's legitimate interests would be significantly harmed
- the proposed publication includes Confidential Information of the objecting Party.

The objection has to include a precise request for necessary modifications.

If an objection has been raised, the involved Parties shall discuss how to overcome the justified grounds for the objection on a timely basis (for example by amendment to the planned publication and/or by protecting information before publication) and the objecting Party shall not unreasonably continue the opposition if appropriate measures are taken following the discussion.

The objecting Party can request a publication delay of not more than 90 calendar days from the time it raises such an objection in case Results are filed for a patent application. At the earlier of properly

addressing the objection or after 90 calendar days the publication is permitted, provided that any justified objection of the objecting Party regarding confidentiality has been properly addressed (including the removal of Confidential Information of the objecting Party).

A Party shall not include in any dissemination activity another Party's Results or Background without obtaining the owning Party's prior written approval. For the avoidance of doubt, publication shall not be deemed to be permitted without the owning Party's prior written approval.

The Parties undertake to cooperate to allow the timely submission, examination, publication and defence of any dissertation or thesis for a degree that includes their Results or Background subject to the confidentiality and publication provisions agreed in this Consortium Agreement.

Supporting this framework, any dissemination/communication activity will be built upon the following guidelines:

- For articles, papers and similar publications, WP9 leader will follow a specific procedure adjusted to the CA rules that will be described in D9.1. This procedure will ensure 1) the quality and correctness of the information about ICT4CART being communicated; 2) the confidentiality aspects.
- For participations at events (workshops, congresses, conferences, etc.), in a similar way, WP9 leader will follow a specific procedure concerning the materials to be used during the event. Concerning the publication of information in ICT4CART electronic tools (as website, newsletter, twitter or LinkedIn groups), given its agile nature, the Project Coordinator, Project Technical Coordinator and WP9 leader will analyse if a given piece of information could have a confidentiality issue; if so, it will be decided either to check for agreement with partners or to cancel the publication in these means.

A detailed procedure (for hard copy material and event attendance), in conformity with GA and CA, has been already available for all consortium partners, through a dedicated wiki page in the internal document repository since M01.

5 Risk management

In ICT4CART, the recognition of risks is considered as an integral and vital part of the project management, in order to anticipate situations that can affect the normal progress of the project. The diversity and complexity of the potential problem and the trans-disciplinary nature of the consortium, increase the number of challenges that may cause issues in the project execution lifecycle.

However, all these issues will be resolved by exploiting the accumulated project implementation experience of the partners and by applying a well laid-out management scheme. Potential risks and related risk mitigation measures have been identified and elaborated since the proposal phase (table 5). In this chapter, the risk management procedures in ICT4CART are thoroughly described.

The ICT4CART Risk Management Plan (RMP) aims to identify and address risks related to i) research, ii) management, and iii) dissemination and exploitation of results, including information on the WPs that could be affected by these risks, their probability of occurrence and the planned mitigation and contingency actions. The RMP will ensure the success of the project by identifying potential problematic and challenging tasks early in advance and envisaging mitigation and contingency measures to avoid or reduce the probability of negative occurrence.

The ICT4CART project will follow the Risk Management Methodology of the Project Management

Institute (PMI)¹ for the project risks. For the software-related risks, it will follow the Software Risk Evaluation (SRE) Methodology² from the Software Engineering Institute (SEI) of Carnegie Mellon University. The basic principle of both methodologies is the continuous discovery, analysis and setting of mitigation strategies for every element of potential project risk. They are both considered essential, aiming to ensure the success of the project.

Starting point for the risk management are the objectives that the consortium wants to reach with the execution of ICT4CART and which might be affected by the occurrence of potential risks. The relevance of the single risks is determined by the combination of two parameters, namely the *probability of occurrence* and the *severity of the impact*. The main risks associated with the project can be divided in two categories: risks internal to the project and risk related to external factors. The consortium will ensure that throughout the project achievements will be measured and the risks re-evaluated throughout the project. Assessment and mitigation of project risks is carried out as follows:

Monitoring and identification of risks:

- Based on half year internal financial and technical reports, mid-term reports and deliverables, the coordinator (administrative part) and the technical manager (technical part) monitor progress in order to identify as early as possible any deviations from the work plan.
- Potential risks defined in the risk matrix are evaluated regularly and updated based on the half year internal reports
- Work package leaders, task leaders and project partners must report any problems to (depending on the specific problem) work package leader, technical manager and/or coordinator.

Assessment risks and mitigation measures:

- Based on the risk matrix, proper measures are elaborated and are implemented (according to the concrete measure, directly with single partners, with work package leaders, via the SC or via the GA or the EC).
- If changes have to be made to the risk assessment, this will be communicated and discussed in the SC and GA and the risk matrix will be updated accordingly by the Risk and Quality Manager.

Table 5 – ICT4CART Critical Risks and mitigation actions

Risk #	WP	Description of Risk	Risk-Mitigation measures	P	D
1	1	Wrong strategic decisions; Diverts developments from major to minor issues due to status misconception	Periodic interim reports where the coordinator asks from all partners and WP leaders an updated status of technical activities and resource consumption; Frequent information exchange in a WP level and also on a consortium-level (plenary meetings, project management teleconferences).	L	H
2	1	Major strategic decision cannot be resolved by, or within, the project	Risk management identifies risks early to leave sufficient time for resolution; Communication management: discussion and conflict resolution culture; Project management: clearly defined escalation hierarchy, use of a mediator if conflict not resolved.	L	M
3	1	A slow start-up phase	A kick-off meeting held early in the project.	L	L

¹ Project Management Institute (PMI) – www.pmi.org

² Daniel Galin, Software Quality Assurance, from theory to implementation, Pearson Addison Wesley (2004)

		may endanger the timing of outcomes expected	Shorter duration milestones to make project manageable. In case risk occurs, tasks split into smaller more manageable sub-tasks to push project developments and aid project be on schedule.		
4	1	Project plans abandoned under pressure, resulting in inefficient development	WP leaders and the Technical Manager will be following the project activities very closely to ensure that project plans are precisely followed by the relevant partners on WP level.	L	H
5	1	Project related decisions are unduly delayed	Implementation of an effective project management structure with clearly defined responsibilities and escalation hierarchies.	L	H
6	1	Project risks are neglected or not adequately managed	Implementation of a project risk management with a Risk Registry and regular review of project risks.	M	H
7	2	Refinement and specification of the ICT4CART use cases is not ready on time	A lot of preparatory work has been carried out to select the four use cases and this will be used as a basis. Even in the case the final use cases are not fully specified on time, the work will start considering the core items of the use cases and will be revised as soon as the final ones will be ready.	M	M
8	2, 3	System requirements, specifications and/or architecture are not ready on time	The implementation work will start considering the core elements of hybrid connectivity, data management and cyber-security, according to the use cases and test sites needs, and will be revised as soon as the final ones will be available.	M	M
9	4	Technical challenges in the realisation of the hybrid communication component	Different approaches for realisation of hybrid connectivity could be deployed in the different test sites. Integration could take place inside the vehicle (on board unit) or at the infrastructure side to ensure a seamless handover. The early start of requirements & specifications will minimise that risk.	L	H
10	4	One or more of the Communication enablers/components (e.g. URLLC, mMTC, slicing, MEC) cannot be implemented	Each of those components is planned to be implemented in at least one test site. In case one of them cannot be realised in any test site for whatever reason, then the impact of this will be analysed and reported in WP4 deliverables. In turn it will be examined if simulation can be used as an alternative in case this risk appears.	L	H
11	5	Technical challenges in the development of the IT environment and the related services	Although this is highly improbable to happen, since there is significant expertise in the consortium in this field and several supporting tools exist, it will be handled with additional iterations with the test sites and with intermediate deliveries (except of the one already defined in M18).	L	H
12	5	The Environment Perception Models	If a complete implementation of the EPMs is not possible, then the most important features of	L	H

		cannot be fully implemented	those models, needed for the realisation of the use cases at the test sites, will be implemented.		
13	6	Technical challenges in the cyber-security and/or data privacy mechanisms implementation	AIRBUS and IBM-Z have already developed similar mechanisms in other activities and they have the needed expertise to adapt them for the needs of ICT4CART. In case this risk occurs, simulation tools could be used to support the implementation.	L	M
14	6	The Supervision Centre cannot be implemented	In case the Supervision Centre cannot be fully implemented, the most important elements (with the highest interest and impact) will be studied i.e. vulnerabilities analysis and data privacy (impersonation of a vehicle).	L	M
15	4, 5, 6	ICT4CART developments regarding connectivity, data and cyber-security are not ready as scheduled to be integrated and tested at the test sites	Actual work on all the technical developments of ICT4CART (WPs 4, 5, 6) starts quite early in the project (M07). Requirements and specifications start even earlier which will support timely delivery. Major and important components needed for the use cases that will take place at the test sites will be tagged with high priority and developed first. Moreover, intermediate deliveries are planned (M18).	L	H
16	7	The integration activities in one or more test sites take more time than planned	The selected parts of the road networks in Austria, Germany and Italy are quite advanced in terms of equipment and digital infrastructure so this is highly improbable. In addition, Task 7.1 starts quite early (M08) to avoid the realization of that risk or even to establish proper measures in case the probability of this happening is increased.	L	M
17	7	One of the ICT4CART test sites cannot be realised	If for whatever reason one of the test sites will not be available for the project, this will not create a significant problem since parts of the developments for this test site could be demonstrated and tested in the other three test sites based on the needed equipment (MEC servers, ITS G5, etc.)	L	L
18	7	Problems with data collection from the test sites	This is highly improbable since the test sites operators are consortium partners and will grant access to all the needed data. In case, some data are not available, simulated data could be used alternatively.	L	M
19	8	Evaluation methodology is not ready by the deadline	Task 8.1 starts well in advance compared to the rest of WP8 tasks which leaves space for a small delay. Several competent partners have been allocated in this task making the probability of realisation of that risk low. Main key performance indicators have been already identified from the proposal phase so they may be refined as soon as the actual ICT4CART infrastructure architecture is ready.	L	L
20	8, 9	Exploitation targets	Clear exploitation goals set out early in the	M	H

		and marker sustainability not clear, measureable or achievable in the given time frame	project and supported by a concise IPR review; exploitation plan covers and balances both incremental improvements as well as significant/revolutionary development steps - must be realistic, measureable and achievable.		
21	9	Failure to properly disseminate the results of the project among the decision making stakeholders	Several partners are in a good position to approach relevant European actors, while others have a wide technical dissemination background. Automotive manufacturers, telecom and IT industries, road operators are participating in the consortium and will disseminate ICT4CART to key stakeholders through their contacts and related associations (e.g. EUCAR, ASECAP, EATA).	L	M
22	9	Low penetration of ICT4CART brand name to the national and EU audience	Development of a precise communication and dissemination strategy; design of an ICT4CART brand story and a website to support dissemination; ICT4CART dedicated social media accounts linked to the corresponding EC ones	M	M
23	9	Not enough critical mass for the engagement of Stakeholders	Developing specific actions (e.g. workshops, awareness campaigns) to attract interest and enhance opportunities and benefits of stakeholders involved in ICT4CART. Partners will also utilise their network of contacts to mobilise them for their active participation.	L	M
24	All	Confrontation among partners for IPR issues	Signature, before starting the project of a Consortium Agreement (CA) taking into account the IPR issues for the whole duration of the project and after the end of the Project; Strict application of the rules defined in the CA.	L	M
25	All	Poor performance of a partner	In ICT4CART there will be a close interaction between coordinator, technical and innovation manager, risk and quality manager, and WP leaders. Therefore, it is possible to identify problems with the quality or timing of the work of single partners early and to react in short time. If a partner does not deliver to work agreed on in the work plan, respective measures are set by the General Assembly (e.g. support of this partner, shift of tasks and related resources).	L	M
26	All	Project partner leaves the ICT4CART project	If a partner should leave the project, the Coordinator and the SC will examine, if partners of the consortium are willing and able to take over the affected tasks. If this should not be the case, it will be decided if the tasks will be taken over by a new partner or if they can be subcontracted. In any case the resources, which have not been used by the leaving partner, will be available to cover the open tasks.	L	M
27	7	There is a certain risk that the national regulators (e.g.	The realisation of this risk (though low) will lead to restrictions on the operation of the Test Sites. Alternative frequency bands will be explored or	L	M

		Bundesnetzagentur in Germany) will impose restrictions on the frequency allocations used on the Test Sites.	at these Test sites the use of ETSI ITS G5 will be enhanced.		
28	7,8	Permission to test autonomous vehicle with trained test drivers could be denied by authorities in Austria (UC2) and Italy (UC4)	The realisation of this risk (though low) will lead to restrictions on the evaluation of the UCs. Alternative solutions in closed roads/environments will be explored.	L	M

6 Information management in ICT4CART

In order to support information exchange and communication within ICT4CART, the following rules and conventions have been defined. In addition, tools have been provided.

Document repository

The project uses the Redmine web-based tool as a document repository and file exchange system, ensuring both safe storage of documents and supporting collaboration among partners.

File naming conventions

Filenames must adhere to the description provided in Section **Error! Reference source not found..**

E-mail conventions

In order to allow efficient use of e-mail the subject must start with "ICT4CART".

Language conventions

For deliverables and all publications, British English must be used.

Confidentiality

Confidentiality is a very important aspect for the work in ICT4CART. Rules and processes concerning confidentiality are described in the Consortium Agreement.

Gender neutral

All communications must be formulated in a gender neutral fashion.

Conclusions

The deliverable provides a description of the procedures need to be applied by the ICT4CART consortium in order to achieve a high quality of project results and a successful management of the project risks. Thus, required project templates have been produced including agenda, attendance form, meeting minutes, presentations and peer review evaluation form, for facilitating the aforementioned actions.

The proposed quality and risk management plan is flexible and well-defined, thus allowing for a robust project monitoring and handling of any problems that may occur. It must be noted that the present

quality and risk management plan is applicable to all the project activities so, compliance with the established procedures is mandatory for all partners involved.

Annex A: ICT4CART Deliverable/Word Template

Grant Agreement Number: 768953

Project acronym: ICT4CART

Project full title: ICT Infrastructure for Connected and Automated

Road Transport

D.X.Y

TITLE

Due delivery date:

Actual delivery date:

Organization name of lead participant for this deliverable: XXX

Dissemination level		
PU	Public	
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the GSA)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the GSA)	
CO	Confidential , only for members of the consortium (including the GSA)	X

Document Control Sheet

Deliverable number:	
Deliverable responsible:	
Workpackage:	
Editor:	

Author(s) – in alphabetical order		
Name	Organisation	E-mail

Document Revision History			
Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
		Modification Reason	Modified by
V0.1			

Abstract
This document presents xxxx

Legal Disclaimer

The document reflects only the authors' view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 768953

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
EC	European Commission
PO	Project officer
GA	Grant Agreement
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

Text

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

Explain why the document is created, what purpose it serves in the project, who are the “customers” e.g. what WPs or Tasks are going to use the deliverable – what question it answers

Text

1.2 Targeted audience

Explained who is the intended audience for the deliverables, e.g. the clients of this deliverables, if public, who is likely to be interested in the content,; research, policy, business

Text

2 Chapter 1

2.1 Sub-heading 1

The first chapter is expected to explain the content and the structure of the document, what will be in the next chapters

Text

2.2 Sub-heading 2

Text ... as shown in **Table 1** below ..

Table 6 – Title 1

2.3 Sub-heading 3

3 Chapter 2

3.1 Sub-heading 1

Text ... as shown in **Table 7** below ..

Table 7 – Title 2

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3.2 Sub-heading 2

3.2.1 Sub heading 3

3.2.1.1 Sub heading 4

Text ... as shown in **Figure 3** below ..

Figure 3 – Title

4 Conclusion

5 Annexes

5.1 Annex 1

Annex B: Deliverable Review Report Template

ICT4CART: ICT Infrastructure for Connected and Automated Road Transport

Review Report for ICT4CART Dx.x Deliverable title

Work package	WPx: Name of WP
Authors	Name-Company (Main author), Name-Company, Name-Company, Name-Company,.....
Dissemination level	Confidential (CO)
Status	Draft
Due date	
Document date	06/12/2018
Version number	x.x
	<i>This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 768953.</i>

The ICT4CART Consortium uses the Deliverable Review process for its internal quality assurance for deliverables to assure consistency and high standard for documented project results.

The Review is done individually by selected reviewers. The author of the document has the final responsibility to collect the comments and suggestions from the Reviewers and decide which changes to the document and actions are to be undertaken.

Reviewers:

Mr/Ms Y (Quality expert) – Company name

Mr/Ms Y (Quality expert) – Company name

Quality Manager:

Panagiotis Lytrivis, ICCS Greece

Overall Review Result

Deliverable is:

<input type="checkbox"/> Fully accepted	<input type="checkbox"/> Accepted with reservation	<input type="checkbox"/> Rejected unless modified as suggested	<input type="checkbox"/> Fully rejected
---	--	--	---

(Double click on the check box you wish to check – a window will open to allow you to check it)

Comments of the Reviewer

Comments of Mr/Ms _____

General comments

These refer to any issue not covered by the particular topics below. They refer to general contents thoroughness, correspondence of the reported work to the project objectives as in the Description of Work and correspondence to the general programme objectives.

Specific comments

Topic A: Relevance

Please answer the question: "Is this deliverable relevant to ICT4CART and to the particular WP activities it covers?"

Reviewer comment

Author response

Topic B: Methodological framework soundness

Please comment on the soundness of the methodology followed and how it is explained. "Are the results arbitrary or based upon a clear methodology, involving users' tests, expert opinions, etc.?"

Reviewer comment

Author response

Topic C: Quality of achievements

Please comment on the essence of the results. "Are they of high value? Are they what one should expect?"

Reviewer comment

Author response

Topic D: Quality of presentation of achievements

Please comment on the results presentation. "Are the results adequately explained and commented or just mentioned? Is there a link between methodology and results?"

Reviewer comment

Author response

Topic E: Deliverable Layout / Spelling / Format

Please comment on the deliverables layout. "Does it include all necessary chapters; is it readable, in comprehensive language, etc.?"

Reviewer comment

Author response

Annex C: ICT4CART Meeting Agenda Template

ICT4CART: ICT Infrastructure for Connected and Automated Road Transport

H2020 Programme

Grant Agreement No: 768953

Agenda

ICT4CART xxxxxxxxxxxxxx Meeting

Date:	dd Month Year
Venue:	City, Country
Organiser:	
Version:	Draft or Final

dd Month Year

Expected participants: ALL partners (or add a Table with participants and affiliation)

Time	Item	Presenter
	<i>Welcome</i>	
	<i>Coffee break</i>	
	<i>Lunch break</i>	
	<i>Coffee break</i>	
	Closing of first day	

Annex D: ICT4CART Meeting Minutes Template

ICT4CART: ICT Infrastructure for Connected and Automated Road Transport

H2020 Programme

Grant Agreement No: 768953

Minutes

ICT4CART xxxxxxxxxxxxxx Meeting

Date:	dd Month Year
Venue:	City, Country
Organiser:	
Version:	Draft or Final

Minutes

dd Month Year

Participants:

Welcome and checking of List of Actions

Topic 1

text

Topic 2

text

List of actions

ID	Action	Who	Deadline	Status	Notes

Annex E: Six-monthly Technical Progress Report Template

ICT4CART: ICT Infrastructure for Connected and Automated Road Transport

H2020 Programme

Grant Agreement No: 768953

Six-monthly Progress Report

Partner:	<Name, Organisation>
Period:	
Date:	YYYY- MM -DD
Version:	v. 0.x

Instructions

For each WP in which you participated in the reporting period please summarise:

WPx

- Work performed by you
- Your achievements in the period
- Problems encountered (if any)
- Deviations from plan and corrective actions (if needed)
- Deliverables and milestones (status), if you are responsible for one of them
- Planned activities for the next reporting period

Annex F: Six-monthly Financial Report Template

An xls file for each member with the following details (ICCS example in the paradigm below)

WP	start	end	Total PlanPMs	Total PMs Spent	Plan PMs P1	Spent PMs P1	Plan PMs P2	Spent PMs P2
WP1	1	36	23,00	0,00	11,50	0,00	11,50	0,00
WP2	1	10	6,00	0,00	6,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
WP3	3	12	11,00	0,00	11,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
WP4	7	30	4,00	0,00	2,00	0,00	2,00	0,00
WP5	7	30	13,00	0,00	6,50	0,00	6,50	0,00
WP6	7	30	6,00	0,00	3,00	0,00	3,00	0,00
WP7	8	32	9,00	0,00	3,96	0,00	5,04	0,00
WP8	13	36	15,00	0,00	3,75	0,00	11,25	0,00
WP9	1	36	12,00	0,00	6,00	0,00	6,00	0,00
Total			99,00	0,00	53,71	0,00	45,29	0,00

Plan PMs M1-M6	Spent PMs M1-M6	STATUS	Justification of deviation	SPENT M1-M6	SPENT M7-M12
3,83	0,00	UNDER		0,00	0,00
3,60	0,00	UNDER		0,00	0,00
4,40	0,00	UNDER		0,00	0,00
0,00	0,00			0,00	0,00
0,00	0,00			0,00	0,00
0,00	0,00			0,00	0,00
0,00	0,00			0,00	0,00
0,00	0,00			0,00	0,00
0,00	0,00			0,00	0,00
2,00	0,00	UNDER		0,00	0,00
13,83	0,00	UNDER		0,00	0,00

Annex G: ICT4CART Presentation Template

This is the template of a Power Point presentation

Subtitle goes here

Dr. Lorem Ipsum
Brussels, 19 October 2018

Section header

Meeting, Date, Place

ict4cart.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's horizon2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 768953

